

Synthesis of Some 2-*p*-Nitrophenylbenzofurans

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Following the observations^{1,2} that the reaction of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide with an *o*-hydroxycarbonyl compound in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in methanol affords a 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofuran, the reaction has been extended by us with a view to preparing a few benzofurans required for some pharmacological studies.

It has been found that the reaction of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide with 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-(I), 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4-methyl-(II) propiophenones, 1-hydroxy-2-propio-(III), 2-hydroxy-1-propio-(IV) naphthones, and 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (V) in methanol in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in course of 45 minutes to one hour furnishes the respective *p*-nitrobenzyloxy derivatives. These form 2,4-DNP and do not show halochromy with H₂SO₄ (conc.).

The *p*-nitrobenzyl ethers, when allowed to react further with anhydrous potassium carbonate in methanol under reflux (time varying from 6 to 9 hours), yield the respective 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans which do not react with carbonyl reagents and show colour reactions with H₂SO₄ (conc.).

2-Hydroxyketones required in the synthesis were prepared through the Fries migration⁴ of the respective phenyl and naphthyl esters. 4-Nitrobenzyl bromide was synthesised by direct bromination of *p*-nitrotoluene³. *p*-Nitrobenzyl ethers of a few *o*-hydroxyketones were prepared by the procedure described by Singh and Verma². The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyketone.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzyloxy derivative.					M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
		R ₁ .	R ₂ .	R ₃ .	R ₄ .	R ₅ .				
1	I	Et	H	Cl	H	H	105°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCl	Cl: 10.92%	11.11%
2	II	Et	H	Cl	Me	H	108°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl	Cl: 10.41	10.65
3	III	Et	H	H	-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	103°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	N: 4.01	4.18
4	IV	Et	-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	H	H	93°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	N: 3.82	4.18
5	V	Me	H	H	Me	H	83°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	N: 5.05	4.91

***2, 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones:**

(I) m.p. 156° (orange); (II) m.p. 198° (orange-yellow); (III) m.p. 175° (orange-yellow); (IV) m.p. 170° (orange); (V) m.p. 142° (orange-yellow).

2-*p*-Nitrophenylbenzofurans were prepared by following the procedure described earlier². The results are recorded in Table II.

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1. Mathur and Mehra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1934.

2. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 49; 1963, 40, 31.

3. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longmans, Green and Company, 1956, p. 961.

4. *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4271.

TABLE II

S.No.	Nitrophenylbenzofuran. R ₁ , R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ , R ₅ .	Colour.	M.P.	Reflux time.	Colour with H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.).	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Et H Cl H H	Yellow	140°	8 hrs.	Red-brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ NCl	Cl: 11.75 %	11.77 %
2	Et H Cl Me H	Deep yellow	143°	9	Deep brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ NCl	Cl: 11.20	11.25
3	Et H H -C ₄ H ₉	Yellow-brown	240°(d)	9	Green	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	N: 3.93	4.42
4	Et -C ₄ H ₉ .. H H	Brown	250°(d)	8	Blue-black	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	N: 4.01	4.42
5	Me H H Me H	Yellow	125°	6	Violet	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	N: 5.00	5.24

(d) denotes decomposition.